

EchoGlove: A Wearable Electronic Glove For Deaf And Dumb

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Abstract—The global percentage of people who are deaf or have significant hearing loss is estimated to be around 5 percent of the world's population (approximately 430 million people) as per the World Health Organization (WHO). To tackle the communication issues faced by the deaf and dumb communities of the present world a wearable glove system is created employing flex sensors to record hand movements and categorize gestures using a hybrid Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model in order to overcome the difficulty of real-time gesture detection for sign language. Through a web-based interface with speech output, the system offers real-time feedback along with effective and precise gesture recognition. The usage of flex sensors, which use machine learning models that record both temporal and spatial data, is a significant design element that lowers hardware complexity and cost while retaining good recognition performance. The technology is expected to have multilingual speech recognition as part of its future scope, which would allow acknowledged gestures to be translated into spoken words in a variety of languages. Additionally, the system will be connected with smart devices and virtual assistants, enhancing communication accessibility for individuals with speech or hearing impairments through a voice-enabled, multilingual interface.

Index Terms— Arduino, Convolution Neural Network, Flex Sensor, Gesture Identification, Long Short Term Memory, Printed Circuit Board

I. INTRODUCTION

Deaf and hard-of-hearing people frequently have communication obstacles, which can result in severe social isolation and an increased risk of depression. With more than 300 languages in use worldwide, sign language—a vital communication tool for this community—is intrinsically complicated. There are particular technological difficulties when translating these languages into spoken or written forms. The creation of practical solutions to improve social interaction and promote inclusivity is necessary to close these communication gaps.

Since even slight changes in movement can drastically change the meaning, sign language gesture identification systems need to use precise techniques to record each gesture's distinct qualities. By immediately recording hand motion data, wearable technology—particularly that which incorporates flexible electronic gloves—offers a viable answer for precise sign language recognition. Real-time gesture interpretation is made possible by this technology, which is crucial for deaf and hard-of-hearing people to

communicate effectively.

Wearable sensor-based systems, as opposed to conventional vision-based systems, offer reliable data collecting independent of background circumstances and lighting, and they also circumvent privacy issues related to video recording. Wearable technology is a good substitute for continuous sign language interpreting because of its straightforward and dependable methodology. Rapid advances in wearable electronics and techno-sensational human-machine interfaces impose great challenges in developing flexible and deformable tactile sensors with high efficiency, ultra-sensitivity, environment tolerance, and self-sustainability [13]. The practicality and utility of these systems in daily life are improved by their capacity to gather precise data in a variety of settings. Gesture recognition has been greatly improved by combining wearable technology with cutting-edge deep learning methods, especially convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and long short-term memory (LSTM) networks. CNNs are very good at capturing spatial data, like the position and form of gestures, which enables the system to recognize the distinct spatial properties of every indication. The precision and effectiveness of gesture recognition can be significantly increased by utilizing these cutting-edge methods. A scalable tactile glove and deep convolutional neural network to show that sensors uniformly distributed over the hand can be used to identify individual objects, estimate their weight, and explore the typical tactile patterns that emerge while grasping objects [12].

In sign language recognition, temporal features are equally important, as gestures involve sequences that unfold over time. LSTM networks, which are designed to recognize patterns in sequential data, help capture the flow and duration of gestures. This capability is essential for distinguishing between similar signs and understanding the nuanced structure of sign language, ensuring that communication remains clear and accurate.

An inventive method for gesture recognition is provided by a parallel architecture that enables CNN and LSTM networks to process spatial and temporal input separately. A parallel technique allows both spatial and temporal characteristics to be extracted simultaneously, improving recognition accuracy, whereas typical systems analyze these features sequentially. This approach tackles the intricacy of sign language, where crucial meaning is conveyed by both gesture shape and movement.

The wearable glove records fine-grained hand motion signals by using flex sensors that identify finger bends, resulting in a comfortable and lightweight solution for everyday use. Each sign is then accurately interpreted by the CNN-LSTM model, which is based on the data gathered from these sensors. In addition to improving identification accuracy, this technology encourages the creation of more approachable gadgets for daily communication.

For the deaf and hard-of-hearing community, this method of sign language detection has the potential to greatly increase accessibility and inclusivity. These technologies promote more social connections in day-to-day life by making communication easier. In the end, combining wearable technology with cutting-edge deep learning methods opens the door to a more welcoming society where everyone can have meaningful discussions without any obstacles.

For these wearables to be successful, deep-learning models must be continuously improved. Artificial intelligence is always evolving, particularly in the area of gesture detection, which guarantees that the technology will eventually become more precise and dependable. The models will be better able to manage the subtleties of many sign languages and the unique signing styles of individual users as they gain knowledge and experience. This flexibility is essential for developing a tool that is really inclusive and able to serve a wide range of users.

Furthermore, these wearable gloves which utilize the use of haptic feedback methods might offer users real-time corrections and confirmations, improving communication and learning. For individuals learning sign language, haptic feedback can act as an instant tutor by warning users of improper motions or validating correct ones. Those who are new to sign language or have recently lost their hearing may find this feature especially helpful.

This technology has an impact on society that goes beyond its users. These gadgets can improve social cohesiveness and community relationships by encouraging improved communication. Deaf and hard-of-hearing people can interact freely and confidently in more inclusive settings, such as public areas, businesses, and schools. A more sympathetic and encouraging society may result from increased awareness and comprehension of the difficulties faced by the deaf community as a result of this inclusivity.

II. RELATED WORKS

Development of the system by integrating hardware prototypes can be observed for sign language recognition using locally sourced materials by integrating three modules an android-based mobile application for input, a control unit

with an ATMEGA 2560 microcontroller, and a robotic hand however the prototype has some limitations. The robotic hand struggles with certain ASL gestures due to the mechanical constraints of the materials used, particularly for complex finger movements. Additionally, the system's accuracy is limited by the precision of the micro-controller and the quality of the input data [5].

A novel development flow for prototyping hand gesture recognition interfaces using distance sensors was presented. Traditional fixed-sensor-based systems are often limited by sensor placement and configuration, making them time-consuming and costly to develop. The proposed method has some limitations. The accuracy of the system is dependent on the quality of the virtual data and the effectiveness of the transfer learning process. Any discrepancies between the virtual and real-world environments can affect recognition accuracy. Additionally, the genetic algorithm, while effective, may not always find the global optimal sensor configuration, potentially impacting system performance [6].

The design and application of wearable gloves recognizes sign language expressions using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network models. Wearable technology has advanced significantly, particularly in the fields of education and communication for the deaf. But for this module the dependency on the LSTM model means that the system's accuracy is heavily reliant on the quality and quantity of training data. Inadequate training data can lead to misrecognition of gestures. Additionally, the mechanical components, such as the DC motors and exoskeleton, may face wear and tear over time, potentially affecting the glove's performance [3].

The correct positioning of sensors is key for a proper system. The accuracy of gesture recognition heavily depends on the quality and positioning of the sensors. Incorrect placement or malfunctioning sensors can lead to misinterpretation of gestures. Additionally, the system's reliance on battery power may limit its usage time, and frequent recharging could be inconvenient[4].

A real-time Indian Sign Language translator using pose estimation and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models. The methodology involves using the INCLUDE dataset, which contains videos of Indian Sign Language signs. The dataset is pre-processed to extract key points from each frame using the MediaPipe Hands module. These key points are normalized and fed into a deep learning model created usingTFLearn. Despite the high accuracy and real-time capabilities, some disadvantages exist. The dependency on the dataset's quality means that variations in signer clothing or background can affect the model's performance.

Additionally, the system's reliance on the MediaPipe Hands module for keypoint detection may introduce errors if the

key points are not accurately detected [10]. A model can be built by using three deep learning models: Simple Recurrent Neural Network (SimpleRNN), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU). Here a physical DC motor is used and the dependency on deep learning models means that the system's accuracy is heavily reliant on the quality and quantity of training data. Inadequate training can lead to misrecognition of gestures. Additionally, the use of DC motors for finger movement control may introduce mechanical limitations and potential wear and tear over time [1].

The use of multi-class classification methods for gesture recognition in presentation settings, comparing K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Decision Tree, Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), and Random Forest are a viable option. But here also despite the promising results, there are some disadvantages to consider. The dependency on machine learning models means that the system's accuracy is heavily reliant on the quality and quantity of training data. Inadequate training can lead to misrecognition of gestures. Additionally, the predefined hand gestures may be difficult for some users to imitate, requiring familiarity with the gestures beforehand [7].

Developing a model without utilizing an LSTM-CNN model poses some problems. A regular Talking gloves model despite its potential, has some disadvantages. The accuracy of gesture recognition heavily depends on the quality and positioning of the sensors. Incorrect placement or malfunctioning sensors can lead to misinterpretation of gestures. Additionally, the system's reliance on battery power may limit its usage time, and frequent recharging could be inconvenient. The prototype's affordability is crucial for widespread adoption, but cost constraints might affect the quality of components used [2].

A robotic hand interpreter system can be developed to aid speech and hard-of-hearing individuals using the Indian Sign Language (ISL) system. The system employs a robotic hand model programmed with a Raspberry Pi 4 to generate signs corresponding to speech commands. Despite its promising results, the robotic hand interpreter system has some limitations. The system struggles to distinguish between certain alphabet pairs, such as 'C' and 'U' or 'H' and 'W,' due to their similar hand shapes. Additionally, the dynamic nature of some signs, like the letter 'J,' poses challenges for the robotic hands. Mechanical limitations and potential wear and tear of the servo motors over time are also concerns [8].

The development of sign language recognition systems, while promising, faces several challenges and limitations across various approaches. Many systems rely heavily on the quality and quantity of training data, with inadequate datasets leading to misrecognition of gestures. Mechanical constraints, such as those in robotic hands or wearable gloves, often limit

the accuracy of complex finger movements and introduce wear and tear over time. Sensor positioning and quality are critical, as incorrect placement or malfunctioning sensors can result in misinterpretation of gestures. Additionally, systems dependent on battery power face usage time limitations and inconvenience due to frequent recharging. Machine learning models, including LSTM, GRU, and others, are sensitive to variations in input data, such as differences in signer clothing or background, which can affect performance. Furthermore, predefined gestures may be difficult for users to replicate, requiring prior familiarity. Cost constraints in prototyping can also compromise the quality of components, impacting overall system reliability and affordability. These limitations highlight the need for continued innovation to address accuracy, durability, and usability in sign language recognition systems.

III. PCB DESIGN AND COMPONENTS

The setup demonstrates a circuit to capture and read analog values from five flex sensors using an Arduino Uno micro-controller. The flex sensors are mounted on a breadboard and are connected in a way that enables the Arduino to read the changes in resistance as each sensor bends. The setup includes components such as the Arduino Uno, flex sensors, resistors, a breadboard, and an LED indicator. The primary purpose of this circuit is to interpret the degree of bending of each sensor, which can then be used to recognize specific gestures in your wearable project for sign language recognition.

A. Components for PCB Design :

The circuit design was done for implementing the hardware essential part of the project and the overall circuit design can be observed from figure 1.

Arduino Uno: The Arduino Uno is the main controller in this setup. It reads analog values from the flex sensors, processes them, and sends output based on these readings. The Arduino's analog pins (A0 to A4) are used to measure the voltage levels from each flex sensor, which correspond to the amount of bending. This information is essential for gesture recognition in the project.

Flex Sensors: The flexible pressure sensor REES52 Flex Bend Sensor (2.2 Inch) is perfect for robotics, gaming, and medical applications since it adjusts resistance in response to bending. It has a response time of less than 10 ms and a flat resistance of 10 ohms, which rises to at least 20 ohms when bent at 180°. The sensor has a lifespan of more than one million bends, operates between -35°C and 80°C, and can withstand pressures ranging from 20g to 10kg. Bending should be restricted to the sensing region to prevent stress

Fig. 1. PCB Design

close to the base and guarantee endurance.

Breadboard: The breadboard organizes the circuit connections and provides a platform to connect all components without soldering. Flex sensors and resistors are mounted on the breadboard, making it easier to create the voltage divider configuration and connect each sensor output to the Arduino.

Resistors (1k each): A 1k resistor is connected in series with each flex sensor, forming a voltage divider circuit. This arrangement is essential because flex sensors output resistance values rather than direct voltages. By adding a fixed resistor in series, the circuit creates a voltage divider where the output voltage varies depending on the sensor's resistance. This varying voltage is what the Arduino reads to determine the bend angle.

LED Indicator with 220 Resistor: This optional LED is connected with a 220 resistor on the breadboard. It acts as a visual indicator and can be programmed to light up based on specific conditions, such as when a particular gesture is detected or when data is successfully being read from the sensors. The LED could serve as a debugging tool, providing immediate feedback on sensor readings or system status.

IV. ARCHITECTURE

The architecture for the wearable sign language recognition system was designed to provide an intuitive and accessible means of communication for the deaf and hard-of-hearing community. The flow of the system can be seen as defined in Fig.2. The overall module consists of the following key

components:

A. Data Collection Module:

This module gathers data from flex sensors embedded in a wearable glove. It captures hand and finger movements, translating them into sign language gestures. This ensures a comprehensive dataset that reflects the nuances of sign language communication.

B. Gesture Recognition Module:

The Gesture Recognition Module is at the heart of the system, responsible for interpreting the data collected from the flex sensors. This module utilizes a combination of Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) to analyze the sequential data captured from the sensors. The LSTM component is particularly effective in recognizing time-dependent patterns in the gesture data, allowing the system to understand the dynamics of gestures as they unfold over time. By training on a diverse set of gesture patterns, the module learns to distinguish between subtle variations in movements, ensuring accurate recognition of sign language gestures. This real-time processing capability is crucial for effective communication, as it allows users to engage naturally without delays.

LSTM-CNN model: The project will leverage CNN and LSTM architectures to enhance gesture recognition accuracy. CNNs are utilized to analyze the spatial features of the gestures captured from the flex sensors, focusing on the geometric and visual aspects of hand movements. This includes interpreting the shape, orientation, and position of the hand during gestures. On the other hand, LSTM

Fig. 2. Architectural Flow

networks are employed to handle the temporal features of the data, capturing the sequence and duration of gestures over time. The combination of CNNs and LSTMs allows for a comprehensive understanding of both the static and dynamic aspects of sign language, improves the model's ability to accurately interpret and classify gestures even when they are performed quickly or with slight variations.

C. Voice Output Module:

Once a gesture is recognized, this component generates corresponding speech output. Utilizing text-to-speech technology, it vocalizes the recognized sign language gestures, facilitating seamless communication between users and their surroundings.

D. User Interface Module:

To provide a seamless experience for users, the project develops a web application that displays the recognized signs in real time and converts them into spoken words. This application features an intuitive user interface (UI) designed to facilitate easy interaction for both deaf and hearing individuals. The real-time nature of the application ensures that users can see their gestures being interpreted instantly, enhancing communication fluidity. Additionally, the application includes visual aids and feedback mechanisms to confirm successful gesture recognition, further improving user engagement. By providing spoken output alongside visual representations of signs, the application bridges communication gaps and fosters inclusivity in various social settings.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Flex Sensor Module:

The Flex Sensor Module is essential for precisely identifying gestures by detecting vital hand motions. The user wears thin, flexible sensors in a glove. These sensors's resistance varies proportionately with finger bend, allowing for the accurate detection of several hand movements. Physical actions are seamlessly transformed into digital data that the system may use for processing. The final image of the physical elements of the project can be seen in Fig 3.

A serial connection was established using a very potent Arduino microcontroller. The glove system and processor unit were able to communicate instantly because of this connectivity. As an interface, the Arduino continuously tracks variations in the flex sensors' resistance before sending the information to the computer for processing. Low latency is ensured by serial connections, allowing for quick, effective, and continuous data flow.

To identify gestures, the flex sensors' incoming data is continuously tracked and processed. The system can precisely read finger locations and movements by mapping particular sensor signals to predetermined gestures. The basis for gesture recognition is this constant flow of processed sensor data, which opens the door to real-time user-system communication.

Fig. 3. Hardware Setup

B. Gesture Recognition Module:

1) Dataset Creation:

One of the most important steps in building a trustworthy recognition system was generating an efficient gesture dataset. In order to capture movement variations, the approach started with manually gathering sensor data for a range of movements, making sure each action was executed several times. This enhanced the system's resilience and flexibility by taking into consideration the inherent variations in how users perform the same motion.

Careful data preparation was done after data collection to guarantee accuracy and consistency. If unfiltered, the noise and volatility in the raw sensor measurements could affect the model's performance. Methods including normalization and smoothing were used to stabilize the data and guarantee consistency across all recorded gestures. The normalization formula is given in Eq 1. To improve the temporal depiction of gestures, measures were also taken to synchronize the time gaps between sensor readings.

$$X_{\text{norm}} = X_{\text{min}} + \frac{X - X_{\text{orig_min}}}{X_{\text{orig_max}} - X_{\text{orig_min}}} \times (X_{\text{max}} - X_{\text{min}}) \quad (1)$$

where:

- X is the original sensor reading.
- $X_{\text{orig_min}}$ and $X_{\text{orig_max}}$ represent the minimum and maximum values in the original dataset.

To facilitate supervised learning, every gesture in the dataset was carefully labeled. During training, accurate labeling made sure the system could link particular sensor

patterns to matching motions. The model was able to learn efficiently thanks to this supervised technique, opening the door for precise hand movement predictions during real-time usage. The foundation of the system's dependable gesture recognition was built on the combination of extensive data collecting, careful pre-processing, and accurate labeling.

2) Model Definition:

The gesture recognition model combines Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks which effectively extract both spatial and temporal characteristics from the flex sensor data and enable precise hand gesture detection,

In essence, CNN layers are utilized to find patterns in the data that correspond to different motions by capturing spatial characteristics from sensor inputs. To extract various properties from the input data, the model uses several convolutional layers with varying kernel sizes (1x1, 3x3, and 5x5). The effective capturing of fine-grained fluctuations in sensor signals is ensured by this multi-scale technique. An activation function (ReLU) comes after each convolutional layer to add non-linearity and improve learning. Max pooling procedures improve generalization and computing efficiency by further reducing the spatial dimensions while maintaining key features.

The CNN part of the model produces spatially processed data that sheds light on how sensor values change in various input gesture components. To comprehend the gesture's general structure, these extracted elements are important.

CNN layers concentrate on spatial information, but gestures also incorporate time-varying dynamic changes. The convolutional layer is responsible for extracting spatial features from the input sensor data by applying a set of learnable filters. Each filter convolves over the input matrix, capturing local patterns and hierarchical representations. The mathematical formulation for the convolution operation is given in Eq 2. The model sequentially combines two LSTM layers to capture these temporal dependencies. The LSTM architecture is perfect for comprehending patterns that emerge over time because it is made to preserve information from earlier time steps. The LSTM layers in this model use the Lambda function to squeeze input data along one axis such that it fits the desired input format.

$$Y(i, j) = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} X(i+m, j+n) \cdot W(m, n) + b \quad (2)$$

where $Y(i, j)$ represents the output feature map at position (i, j) , $X(i+m, j+n)$ denotes the input feature map, $W(m, n)$ is the convolutional kernel of size $M \times N$, and b is the bias term. The summation operation iterates over all filter elements, multiplying them with corresponding input

values before summing the results. This process enables the model to capture distinctive spatial patterns crucial for gesture recognition.

The first LSTM layer processes initial temporal dependencies, which then forward the data to the second LSTM layer for a more thorough comprehension of sequential patterns. These layers aid the model in understanding minute variations in hand motions, like shifting finger positions. Lastly, the Lambda function is used to restructure the processed LSTM output to the necessary dimensions for subsequent operations.

The system efficiently recognizes complicated gestures in real time by fusing the temporal analysis of LSTM with the spatial feature extraction capabilities of CNN, providing stronger performance

C. Voice Output Module:

1) Translation of Gestures into Textual Representations:

Each gesture predicted by the Para-LSTM-CNN model was linked to a predefined textual description. For example, a gesture representing the letter "A" in American Sign Language (ASL) was associated with the text "A." This association was implemented using a dictionary-based approach, where numerical labels corresponding to specific gestures were mapped to their respective textual outputs. This step ensured that the system could accurately interpret and represent the predicted gestures in a format suitable for voice synthesis.

Once the gesture predictions were mapped to their corresponding text descriptions, the system dynamically generated text outputs in real time. This process involved continuously updating the text output based on the latest gesture predictions from the model. The integration of the gesture prediction pipeline with the text mapping module ensured minimal delay between gesture recognition and text generation. This capability was essential for providing immediate feedback to users, making the system effective for real-time sign language translation.

2) Speech Synthesis Using iOS Built-in Voice API:

The iOS built-in voice API was employed to deliver high-quality, system-level text-to-speech functionality. This API supports multiple languages and voice options, ensuring adaptability to diverse user needs. The TTS functionality was accessed programmatically using Python commands, enabling the system to trigger voice output based on the generated text descriptions. By utilizing the native iOS TTS capabilities, the system achieved reliable and efficient speech synthesis without relying on external third-party libraries.

The system used Python's `os.system()` command to invoke the iOS TTS API and produce voice output in real time. Each text description corresponding to a predicted gesture

was passed to the TTS API, which converted it into audible speech. The system was designed to handle a wide range of gestures seamlessly, ensuring that each gesture was accurately represented in both text and speech formats. This synchronization was achieved by maintaining a consistent mapping between gestures, text descriptions, and voice outputs, enabling the system to function effectively across various sign language gestures.

D. User Interface Model:

A user-friendly web interface was designed to facilitate gesture recognition and real-time feedback. Flask, a Python-based web framework, was chosen for its simplicity and flexibility in building web applications. The interface was designed with a clean and intuitive layout, allowing users to easily interact with the system. Key elements such as input fields, display areas, and control buttons were incorporated to enhance usability and accessibility. The web interface was equipped with a real-time gesture display feature, which visually presented the recognized gestures to the user. This feature was implemented by integrating the gesture recognition pipeline with the Flask-based front end.

As the system processed input data from the flex sensor-equipped glove, the corresponding gestures were dynamically updated on the web interface. This real-time feedback mechanism ensured that users could immediately see the results of their gestures, enhancing the overall user experience.

Flask was employed to create the web application interface due to its lightweight architecture and ease of integration with Python-based backend systems. The framework allowed for the seamless connection of the gesture recognition model and voice output module to the web interface. Flask's routing capabilities enabled the creation of multiple endpoints, ensuring smooth communication between the front end and backend components.

VI. RESULTS

The ability of the suggested sign language recognition system to anticipate hand gestures captured by flex sensors was evaluated. To ensure a representative and diverse input set, the model was trained using gesture labels with 5000 reads each.

Throughout multiple training epochs, accuracy and loss were measured to gauge the model's effectiveness. The training vs. validation accuracy and training vs. validation loss curves showed that the model achieved 99% accuracy with minimal loss convergence. These findings show that the model had a good prediction ability and low overfitting after learning to recognize hand motions. Figure 4 and 5 depict

the accuracy of the electronic glove

Fig. 4. Training vs Validation Accuracy

Fig. 5. Training vs Validation Loss

The accuracy curve shows a sharp rise in performance during the first few epochs, with a stabilization near 99%. This little enhancement demonstrates how well the LSTM-CNN architecture captures temporal and spatial dependencies in the gesture data indicating that it generalizes to new inputs

well, enabling consistent gesture recognition.

Similarly, the loss curve exhibits a notable decline during the initial training phase before stabilizing at a low value in subsequent epochs, signifying efficient learning without overfitting. The quick drop in loss values in the early epochs indicates that the model quickly adjusts to the dataset's patterns. The loss stabilizes as training goes on, indicating that the model has mastered the underlying gesture patterns. Even when exposed to invisible gestures, the system is guaranteed to retain a high prediction accuracy thanks to this stability. The performance of the model was contrasted with that of previous flex sensor-based sign language recognition techniques to verify its robustness. The accuracy of various models is compared in Table 1.

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT GESTURE RECOGNITION MODELS

Model / Approach	Accuracy
Multilayer Perceptrons (MLPs) with Flex Sensor Gloves[16]	97.6%
Template Matching Algorithm with Smart Glove Embedded with Flex Sensors[17]	94.5%
K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN) with Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) using Sensory Glove[18]	96.6%
Para LSTM - CNN Model with Smart Glove Embedded with Flex Sensors(Proposed Model)	99%

All of these methods were surpassed by the LSTM-CNN model, which achieved more accuracy while successfully capturing the temporal and spatial interdependence of hand motions.

The outcomes demonstrate the great efficacy of the LSTM-CNN architecture for flex sensor sign language recognition. It performs better than conventional machine learning models because it can learn both spatial (CNN) and temporal (LSTM) features. These results demonstrate how deep learning-based wearable technology can help the deaf and mute communities communicate in real time.

VII. CONCLUSION

In the final stages of development, the project has successfully achieved its objectives, marking a significant milestone in sign language communication technology. The hardware connections and input sensor values from the flex sensors were meticulously set up and calibrated. The integration of the Arduino Uno with the flex sensors proved effective, enabling real-time monitoring of the bending movements. The tests confirmed that varying degrees of bending correspond to specific analog readings, validating the feasibility of using these sensors for gesture recognition. Through precise calibration and testing, reliable data was gathered, establishing a robust mapping between sensor

readings and recognized gestures, thereby ensuring accurate sign language interpretation.

With the hardware fully configured and comprehensive testing completed, the project shifted focus to enhancing gesture recognition capabilities and integrating voice output. These advancements have culminated in the development of a highly effective and user-friendly system for sign language communication. The wearable glove, powered by deep learning models, now accurately interprets a wide range of gestures and translates them into audible or written language, greatly facilitating communication for deaf and hard-of-hearing individuals.

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